

The impact of standard-setting knowledge networks on firm innovation

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates mechanisms behind firm-level innovation that is fostered by participation in technical standard-setting. Motivated by the distinct nature of knowledge exchange in the standardization context, we relate knowledge networks formed by standard co-authorship with firms' patent output. Results from panel regression show that the extent and content of knowledge exchange and the attainment of brokerage positions are significant determinants. Our findings imply that firms can increase their innovation output by becoming brokers between disconnected standardization sub-networks, and by interacting with technologically distant partners. Considering knowledge integration costs, we find that both effects are inverted U-shaped. These results offer valuable insights for both managers and researchers by illuminating the distinctive knowledge exchange mechanisms in standardization and guiding strategic participation.

1. Introduction

Firms and other stakeholders cooperate and compete at standard-setting organizations to produce technical standards. These documents are established based on formalized processes that often include creating consensus among expert participants in a variety of technical committees and working groups. Examples for well-known types of standards include the international ISO-standards, such as the famous ISO 9001 quality management series, but also standards established on regional or national level.

Although the primary goals of these standardization processes are to achieve higher levels of compatibility and quality, there are “side effects” that have been the subject of research. Especially the relationship between standardization and innovation has received great attention. Studies have produced evidence for a positive relationship on macroeconomic level (Blind & Jungmittag, 2008).

More recently, research has also produced evidence on firm level. Studies show that firms can benefit from participation in standard-setting (Goluchowicz & Blind, 2011; Nambisan, 2013; Wakke et al., 2012, 2016; Zhang et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2018) and that they strategically engage in standardization due to its potential contribution to innovation (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016; Liefner et al., 2019).

Yet, the firm-level relationship has so far remained a “black box” as there is a lack of evidence on the *determinants* for this effect. How could participation contribute to firm-level innovation? Which firms benefit the most?

In this article, we investigate knowledge exchange as a key mechanism behind the effect of participation in standardization on firm-level innovation (e.g., Zhang et al., 2020). We focus on collaboration, and the exchange and recombination of knowledge as central aspects of the standard-setting process (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016; Delcamp & Leiponen, 2014).

We argue that, in order to create and find consensus on new or adapted standards, firms search and evaluate a space of alternative technological solutions that could serve as potential standards (Xie et al., 2016). They exchange and recombine knowledge across firm boundaries in order to arrive at rules that satisfy various technical and political requirements and create interfaces between already implemented technologies. Knowledge exchanged during standard-setting is, therefore, often unique and diverse—ideal conditions for firms to increase their innovation potential.

The exchange is embedded in inter-organizational knowledge networks (Bar & Leiponen, 2014; Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2013; Phelps et al., 2012). Differences in access to knowledge and resulting benefits for innovation are therefore related to firms' positions in the network. Firms with *broker status* (Burt, 2004; Hargadon, 2002) that connect different technological fields across structural holes (Burt, 2004), have access to more new knowledge and, therefore, potentially receive most innovation gains (Lee, 2010).

In addition to network structure, we also account for knowledge content, and refer to firm's *technological distance* to their interaction

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partners. Technological distance is related to firms' efforts to absorb and integrate knowledge from exchanges in standard-setting, and there can be an optimal distance at which firms maximize resulting innovation outcomes (Nambisan, 2013; Nooteboom et al., 2007; Subramanian et al., 2018).

In order to test our concept empirically, we created a panel dataset that includes information on networks formed by the co-authorship of standards, based on seven years of standard-setting activity in the French chemical industry. We then used this data to regress firm-level topology metrics on firms' subsequent patent applications as innovation output indicators.

Our results indicate that innovation output after participation in standardization is positively related to firms' brokerage positions in the generated inter-firm networks. Technological distance in committees has an inverted U-shaped relationship with subsequent innovation.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. We first present the theoretical background (Section 2), focusing on knowledge exchange in the standardization process as an antecedent for innovation effects. We identify properties of standardization networks as determinants for effect size and accordingly derive our hypotheses. In the following section, we describe the collection of standards authorship information and patent data 3.1, define our regression model 3.3 and the operational standardization network model based on co-authorship 3.2. Next, we define the dependent, independent and control variables for regression (Section 3.4). Section 4 presents descriptive statistics, regression results, and robustness checks. Finally, we discuss our results and their implications for theory and practice (Section 5), before concluding with managerial implications and recommendations for further research (Section 6).

2. Theory and hypotheses

2.1. Standardization and innovation

The relationship between standardization and innovation has been a key topic for standardization researchers in the last two decades (Blind, 2019; Blind et al., 2017a; Swann, 2010). Contrary to previously assumed stifling effects on innovation (e.g., Maxwell, 1998), more standardization can indeed be associated with higher innovation output (Blind, 2013; Zoo et al., 2017) and economic growth (Blind & Jungmittag, 2008). Literature mainly attributes this to the role of standards in markets, where they support the diffusion of codified knowledge and new rules. Standards further help to establish compatibility and minimum quality levels and reduce transaction costs and technological variation. This amplifies network effects and creates "ecosystems" around selected solutions that promote developing new products and processes (Blind, 2004; Swann, 2000; Tassej, 2000).

On the firm level, innovation and standardization activity likely have a reciprocal relationship. On the one hand, more innovative firms are more likely to participate in standard-setting. On the other hand, firms that participate might have a higher innovation output.

The former effect is related to firms using standardization as an appropriation mechanism for rents from innovation. By being involved in standard-setting, firms can retain technology-specific R&D investments. They can assure that markets' technological trajectories do not move away too far from the firms' (Antonelli, 1994) and that their innovations receive more trust in different stages of market adoption (Viardot, 2017). Firms therefore increase user-bases and benefits from network effects by inserting own technology into standards. Owning patents for technology that becomes essential for the implementation of certain standards is often associated with significant increases in licensing income (Pohlmann et al., 2016).

The interaction with law-makers, particularly in formal standardization, gives firms the option to influence the implementation of market regulation. This is most evidently the case when laws refer to mandated standards to specify concrete state-of-the-art requirements (e.g., under

the EU's "New Approach", Heß & Blind, 2019). This can entail further positive effects for diffusion and legitimacy (Botzem & Dobusch, 2012).

However, firms need to balance the benefits of including their technology in standards, and the dangers that disclosure brings for the protection of their intellectual property (Toh & Miller, 2017). Firms that are already in a strong market position might therefore have lower incentives to standardize (Blind & Thumm, 2004). Highly innovative firms could choose other appropriation mechanisms before participating in standardization (Baron et al., 2018). The relationship between firms' innovation and their propensity to participate in standardization is therefore assumed to be inverted U-shaped (Wakke et al., 2015).

2.2. The role of knowledge exchange in standardization

The opposing effect, increasing innovation potential through participation, is often attributed to the role of knowledge exchange during standard-setting (Nambisan, 2013; Wakke et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2018).

In standardization committees, firms introduce proposals for new or adapted rules, based on their prior R&D and existing technology. In order to convince other participants to agree to these rules, their technical descriptions often need to disclose highly detailed internal knowledge (Sherif, 2015). Firms' efforts to improve their market position by shaping standards to their needs thus result in knowledge spillovers to other firms (Alexy et al., 2013). Firms that show more R&D intensity and potentially a higher absorptive capacity tend to motivate their participation in standardization by knowledge seeking. Especially large firms participate and disclose knowledge to influence regulation, while SMEs participate with the aim of profiting from the exposed knowledge of larger firms (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016).

As a result, the standard-setting context functions as a knowledge transfer channel and a forum with a high potential for "learning about new and emerging technologies" (Nambisan, 2013; Schmidt et al., 1998, p. 97). Committees serve as *vantage points* where firms can overlook developments in technologies and markets as the involved experts share information about internal innovation. By using this knowledge, firms are able to proactively adjust their R&D and produce more successful innovations. Firms' standardization activities can therefore be explicit strategies of extending internal R&D processes through external knowledge sourcing (Bar & Leiponen, 2014; Großmann et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2018).

This perspective is reinforced by statements of firms that quote knowledge exchange as an important motive for participating in standard-setting organizations (Bar & Leiponen, 2014; Blind, 2013; Blind & Heß, 2020; Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016; Wakke et al., 2015). It is also visible in the behavior of latecomer firms that, as part of their knowledge-seeking strategy, invest considerable effort into gaining access to committees with particularly valuable knowledge (Liefner et al., 2019). Likewise, on an international level, standards organizations have represented "interactive learning spaces" (Sherif, 2015, p. 114) in the technological catch-up processes of economies (Ernst et al., 2014; Kang et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2005).

Especially in open consensus-finding contexts, i.e., most formal standardization (Baron et al., 2019), knowledge is provided by a variety of stakeholders, including firms in different market positions, such as competitors, suppliers, customers, as well as universities, societal stakeholders, and government entities. Participating in standardization therefore increases firms' alliance portfolio diversity, which is associated with increased innovation performance (e.g., De Leeuw et al., 2014). Particularly the combination of market-driven with technology-driven input through the integration of universities in standard development (Blind & Gauch, 2009; Blind et al., 2018) can provide firms with increased opportunities for new knowledge creation and innovation (Fabrizio, 2009; Jensen et al., 2007; Kafouros et al., 2015; Sofka & Grimpe, 2010).

Additionally, highly standardized processes and codified outputs can reduce efforts for knowledge absorption and simplify firms' exploratory search of more knowledge. Firms that are active in standardization might therefore find it easier to access a larger number of knowledge sources and higher knowledge breadth, leading to more successful innovation (Leiponen & Helfat, 2010).

Further aspects concerning knowledge type and participants are potentially relevant in this context. Standards are the product of a process that involves the collaborative establishment and assessment of competing or complementary technological solutions and non-technological (political) constraints. This process can be understood as distributed search in a space of tacit and explicit knowledge about potential solutions and a transformation into codified knowledge (Xie et al., 2016). This simultaneity of knowledge exchange, recombination and an interplay of tacit and explicit knowledge suggest that standardization is an environment in which firms can increase their knowledge base and produce innovations (Ahuja et al., 2008; Savino et al., 2017).

On the level of individual participants, exchange of complex and tacit knowledge can be fostered by the build-up of social capital (Filiari & Alguezaui, 2014), the forming of *communities of practice* (Dokko & Rosenkopf, 2010), a context of joint problem-solving and frequent communication (McEvily & Marcus, 2005), and the intrinsic motivation of standardization experts (Blind et al., 2018; Lam, 2011).

Knowledge gathered from standardization committees can be particularly conducive to innovation if it is technologically distant from a firm's existing knowledge base, thereby providing more non-redundant information (Nambisan, 2013). However, more technological distance can create higher cognitive efforts to absorb and integrate new knowledge (Nooteboom et al., 2007). Combining such opposing effects, technological distance to individual partners has been shown to have an inverted U-shaped relationship with interfirm learning in strategic alliances (Subramanian et al., 2018).

Depending on the type of innovation produced, the combined effects of an extended knowledge base might yield different shapes. Generally, findings pertaining to firm alliances indicate that partner-type diversity is positively associated with exploitative (incremental) innovation and has an inverted U-shaped relationship with explorative (radical) innovation (De Leeuw et al., 2014). Nambisan (2013) showed for the case of standard-setting, that the extent of participation in *both* technologically *close* and *distant* technical committees (TCs) has an inverted U-shaped relationship to innovation output. The effect separation is based on the distinction between exploitative (competence-enhancing) innovation from participation in close TCs, and exploratory (new competence) innovation from distant (or peripheral) TCs.

2.3. Standardization networks

Assessing knowledge exchange as a determinant for subsequent innovation must take into account that standard-setting is a distributed activity that involves collaboration in different organizations, committees and subgroups (Lerner & Tirole, 2004). Varying participant compositions embed firms in a diverse structure of inter-organizational relationships (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2013). The configurations of such "standardization networks" are, on the one hand, a determinant in decision-making and consensus-finding (Leiponen, 2008). On the other hand, connections in standard-setting also reflect knowledge exchange and coordination of innovation (Delcamp & Leiponen, 2014). The structure of standardization networks can therefore be considered a determinant for the extent and type of knowledge exchange and induced innovation.

We propose that varying (and changing) compositions of standard-setting groups create knowledge exchange structures that can be represented as *knowledge networks* (e.g., Phelps et al., 2012). Networks consist of "channels and conduits for knowledge" (Owen-Smith & Powell, 2004), and connect firms as knowledge sources and sinks. The more knowledge sources a standardizing firm connects to, the more

knowledge it can potentially gather from its participation, thereby increasing the innovation potential.

Firms use standardization networks to source knowledge from other firms and stakeholders from science, government and society. Different knowledge sources can offer varying extents and types of knowledge, which is a product of their pre-existing knowledge base and their recursive connection to other knowledge sources. A firm's knowledge network embeddedness determines the knowledge flows that pass through it and subsequently, associated innovation benefits.

From the perspective of recombinatory search leading to innovation, firms benefit from sharing knowledge with a wide and diverse set of sources (Savino et al., 2017). Firms that are centrally positioned in a network experience more knowledge sharing (Ahuja, 2000). Especially firms that bridge *structural holes* ("gaps" between groups in a network, Burt 2004) and connect otherwise disconnected firms, have access to extended and diverse knowledge. They take on *brokerage positions* and facilitate exchange in knowledge networks (Burt, 2004; Hargadon, 2002).

Standardizing firms can act as brokers if they are co-developing standards with firms that are not directly cooperating themselves. As firms often only participate in a single or a few technical committees, co-development structures are likely to consist of dense clusters that are weakly connected among each other. Firms assume broker positions between clusters when they participate in a high number of committees or in an uncommon combination of committees, e.g., because of a unique technological specialization.

Their unique positions allow brokers to take on special functions in the interaction between groups (Fernandez & Gould, 1994). In the standardization process, one function can be coordinating between multiple committees, e.g., to assure consistency between new standards. This can also mean acting as gatekeepers that collect knowledge from other distant committees which they then pass on to their local group. Vice versa, brokers can represent local groups by transporting their knowledge to actors outside their boundaries.

Brokers in knowledge networks bridge structural holes and thereby connect a high number of potentially diverse knowledge sources. By bundling a high number of knowledge flows, they can increase their knowledge bases. From a recombinatory search perspective, this increases their innovation potential. Standardizing firms take on broker status when they connect technical committees that would otherwise not be connected. Brokering firms transfer knowledge about technological developments and new rules between committees. They act as connecting interfaces between technological fields and contribute to coordinating and creating consistency in the standards landscape. This vantage position is associated with increased access to diverse knowledge, thereby fostering their innovation potential (Lee, 2010).

However, the additional benefit of stronger brokerage positions likely has diminishing returns. Adding more and more knowledge flows contributes less and less to new knowledge (Deeds & Hill, 1996), as additional flows likely contain redundant knowledge that has already been integrated. More brokerage, i.e., the integration of further knowledge domains, might "exhaust the productive search space" and not yield additional recombinative value (Hsu & Lim, 2014). With additional brokerage, the total amount of accessed knowledge approaches the sum of all knowledge exchanged in the network. Even more, standardizing firms could reach thresholds at which additional centrality and associated knowledge flows over challenge their knowledge absorption and integration capacities (Paruchuri, 2010).

2.4. Hypotheses

Based on the theory presented in the preceding sections, we formulate two hypotheses regarding the effect of standardization activity on innovation output. As presented, we assume that additional innovation output can be attributed to an increase in accessible knowledge through direct interactions in committees and working groups (and through

Fig. 1. Conceptual model with temporal setup. Collaborations on standards form standardization networks that determine innovation output, measured in patent applications.

Fig. 2. Overview of hypotheses.

informal contacts) and indirectly from shared documents. We focus our hypotheses on properties of these interactions, which we assume to be determinants for individual firms’ access to knowledge, the extension of knowledge bases, and, subsequently, the increase of innovation outputs.

First, we consider the diversity of directly accessed knowledge. As presented in Section 2.2, a combination of two latent functions (Haans et al., 2015) appears to be likely. On the one hand, when more diverse knowledge is accessed, it is likely less redundant. This leads to stronger growth of knowledge bases. On the other hand, more diverse (and therefore more likely distant) knowledge could create higher integration costs, or might even contain a higher proportion of irrelevant or unusable knowledge. We assume that the total effect of knowledge diversity on a firm’s knowledge base is the difference between these benefits and costs. Returns from more diversity are likely diminishing, and are bounded by a maximum level of diversity and the overall accessible sum of knowledge available in the network. Integration costs are likely rising exponentially with diversity due to combinatorial effort. Accordingly, we assume that the total effect (the sum) is inverted U-shaped (see Fig. 2).

For purposes of operationalization, we propose technological distance as a proxy for knowledge diversity, similar to Nambisan (2013). This assumes that committees, in which participants are, on average, more technologically distant, offer more knowledge diversity. Also considering Nambisan (2013)’s findings on the relationship between firms’ innovation output and technological similarity with TCs, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 1 (H1). Standardizing firms’ innovation output has an inverse U-shaped relationship with technological distance to their co-standardizers.

Second, we consider the amount of indirectly accessed knowledge in association with firms’ positions in the standardization network. According to the theory presented in Section 2.3, we assume that firms which are positioned such that they facilitate more knowledge exchange between structural holes in the network (brokers), can access more additional knowledge. Here, the same latent functions apply as in the construction of hypothesis 1. Additional brokerage likely yields diminishing additional accessed knowledge due to increasing redundancy, while integration costs could rise exponentially due to combinatorial effort. The difference of benefits and costs results in a total effect that is inverted U-shaped:

Hypothesis 2 (H2). Standardizing firms’ innovation output is associated with brokerage in standardization networks; the relationship is inverse U-shaped.

3. Methodology

Our aim is to investigate the effect of standardizing firms’ network positions and technological distance on their innovation output as the product of knowledge gathered during standard-setting. Accordingly, we regress firms’ network position and technological distance on their innovation output.

In this section, we first discuss the used data and then explain the setup and estimation of our regression model. We then operationalize the concept of a knowledge network formed by collaboration in the development of standards (“standardization network”) and define the dependent variable innovation output, the independent variables brokerage, technological distance, and control variables.

3.1. Data

We focused our analysis on the French national standards body AFNOR as it is one of the few SSOs that publishes (or rather, published) the authors of its standards. The development process of standards at AFNOR is similar to that of other formal SSOs (Baron et al., 2019), and is governed by a complex set of rules (NF X50-088:2009; AFNOR, 2017) that is aimed at guaranteeing openness and transparency and the adequate representation of different stakeholder groups (including government, industry, science, consumers, unions, etc.).

As standard-setting at formal SSOs is an open process, interested firms and other stakeholders self-select into relevant committees. They can have different motives for participation, such as wanting to influence the technological development of relevant areas, seeking knowledge from other market players, or preempting public regulation (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016). Participation in standard-setting is usually an activity performed by larger and slightly more innovative firms. A representative survey of German firms (Blind et al., 2022) shows that around 12% of all firms are active in standardization. This activity is often combined with patenting, as “39% of patenting firms develop standards” and “30% of the firms developing standards apply for patents” (Blind et al., 2022).

AFNOR standards are the result of standardization projects, which are initiated by administrative offices within AFNOR, and either passed to an existing technical committee (national TCs: called *commission de normalization*), or the domain-specific strategic committee (*comité stratégique*) that sets up a new technical committee. The SSO office is responsible for including suitable experts (the subsequent authors of the standards) that are affiliated with relevant organizations. The development phases then entail the development of an initial standard draft, which undergoes public inquiry and has to meet general consensus before finalization and approval.¹

We used web-scraping to set up a meta-data base for more than 60,000 documents that were the output of this development process, including standards (in different revision versions), draft standards, and technical rules/specifications. A comparison with official statistics from AFNOR and checking a standards-database (formerly “Perinorm”, now “Nautos”) validated that we covered the complete corpus of standards documents published by AFNOR.

Authors’ affiliations required extensive manual reconciliation and correction, as they were often affected by errors from manual input or optical character recognition (typos, switched characters, variations of acronyms, different firm subdivisions and regional branches, etc.). In order to be able to base our analysis on consistent, clean data, we decided to select a sub-sample of the whole data set and clean it manually.

The selection of a single industry from this data set was based on two considerations. On the one hand, the reduction of our data set to increase the feasibility of manual analyses. On the other, selecting a large enough and economically relevant industry with high standardizing and patenting activity that would provide enough variance in the data. We found that the French chemical industry satisfied these requirements. France was the second largest exporter of chemicals in the EU in 2009. The manufacture of chemicals and chemical products

(NACE rev.2/C 20) generated a turnover of €66.5 billion, second highest in the EU. The industry consisted of about 2800 firms, building on one of Europe’s largest regional chemicals manufacturing workforces in the cluster of Île-de-France. About two-thirds of French chemical manufacturers were SMEs, plus a number of large multinational corporations, such as Arkema, Air Liquide, L’Oréal, or Total Petrochemicals. With €1.03 billion, the industry provided about 4% of French industrial R&D expenses (all data EUROSTAT, 2009).

We used the supplied document classifications (which followed International Organization for Standardization (ISO)’s International Classification for Standards, ICS) to select all documents related to *products of the chemical industry* (such as gases, cosmetics, explosives, paint etc.). An analysis of the publication activity of organizations by ICS indicated that this approach to sample selection was an intuitive and realistic method that also reduced the loss of potential knowledge flows.

Firms’ activity by *topic* (ICS) showed to be a determining factor for the emergence of distinct standardization areas, which was evident in the low number of firms that authored standards across different ICS classes. Most firms focused their activity on standards classified under a single top-level ICS class. The fraction of firms being active in projects classified under different (toplevel-) ICS lay below 10%. Only few firms showed more diverse activity in semantically similar ICS classes (e.g., ~20% overlap between “Textile and leather technology” and “Clothing industry”), or complementary classes such as “Construction materials and building” and “Environment, Health protection, and Safety”.

We manually collected patent data using the Iplytics platform,² which provided enhanced access to official data from patent offices and simplified the aggregation of relevant patent applicants (firm divisions, subsidiaries, joint ventures).

3.2. Network model

We model the knowledge exchange between standardizing firms as a *knowledge network* (Phelps, 2010). In most standard-setting organizations (SSOs), a *technical committee* is an organizational shell that is dedicated to a certain technological area and that manages the publication of new or updated standards. Per standard, committees commonly have dedicated sub-groups with different members, that constitute the context for meetings and the exchange of documents such as technical proposals.

We view these groups as the centers of knowledge exchange, and propose that all members gain equal access to the codified (but not necessarily published), or tacit, knowledge exchanged therein (a “non-rivalrous club good”). In order to identify group members, we refer to the authorship information on a group’s published documents. These are mainly standards, but can include draft standards, or technical specifications, etc.

We consequently model a *standardization network* as a firm-level knowledge network, where links between all such firms exist that are co-authors of at least one published document. As new firms enter committees and sub-groups, and other firms leave, the network changes. We assume that the knowledge exchange happens in a time interval between a group’s establishment, and the publication of its final deliverable, and that links in the network, therefore, only exist in that same interval.

We represent the standardization network as a graph $G = (F, C)$, which is a tuple of firm vertices $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ and undirected edges $C \subset F^2$. For every document d from a subset of relevant documents published by a SSO, we take into account the set of authoring firms $F_d \subset F$, and the time interval of collaborative development τ_d , ending at the time of document publication.

¹ More details on the process are published by AFNOR. See NF X50-088:2009 and <https://www.afnor.org/en/standards/standards-definition/>.

² <https://www.iplytics.com/>

As data on starting dates of collaborations was not available to us, we approximate collaboration duration with a constant k number of years. We set k to 3, which is the average time of standard development in international standardization.³ The network is defined by the connections that firms create among each other during the collaboration-phase of each document.

We, therefore, model a time-varying network $G(\tau) = (F(\tau), C(\tau))$ at time τ by its population of firms $F(\tau) = \bigcup_{F_d} \forall d \in D(\tau)$ that were part of the committees that, at that time, worked on the standards $D(\tau) = \{d \mid \tau \in \tau_d\}$. Firms are connected in the network if they are co-authors of at least one document that was under development at time τ :

$$C(\tau) = \{(f_i, f_j) \mid i \neq j \wedge f_i, f_j \in F_d \wedge d \in D(\tau)\}.$$

In order to set up a panel structure for regression, we discretize this representation into interval networks. We take yearly snapshots denoted with index t , so that $\tau \in I_t$, and, e.g., $t = 2000 \implies I_t = [1/1/2000, 12/31/2000]$. The network in the snapshot of year t is based on all standards that were under development in that year: $D_t = \{d \mid \tau_d \cap I_t \neq \emptyset\}$, and equivalently all involved firms $F(\tau)$ and their connections $C(\tau)$ for all $\tau \in I_t$.

3.3. Regression model

Using the collected data on networks and patenting activity, we perform panel regression with firm-level fixed effects and lagged independent variables to test our hypotheses. Firms' innovation output (Fig. 1) is defined as a function of their brokerage position in the standardization network and the technological distance to their direct neighbors.

As gathered knowledge needs to be absorbed and fed into R&D processes, we expect a delay between activity in standardization and the associated innovation output. This delay is potentially increased by process times of R&D and patenting. While R&D and patent output can be almost simultaneous, some of the effects of R&D investments can be delayed by multiple years (Gurmu & Pérez-Sebastián, 2008; Hall et al., 1986; Kondo, 1999).

Measuring delayed (leading) patent applications also avoids including strategic “just-in-time patenting” behavior of firms (Kang & Bekkers, 2015) that reflects prior innovation rather than innovation stemming from the investigated standard-setting effort.

In order to capture different delay structures, we model the cumulative sum of patent applications filed in a time span after standardization activity. We consider a maximum of 5 years lead (similar to Phelps, 2010). We control for firms' lagged (pre-sample) innovation output and relevant aspects of the overall topology of the network in year t . As we expect technological distance and brokerage to have U-shaped relationships with innovation output, we include their squared terms.

Our model is, therefore:

$$\text{inno}_{i,\gamma} = f(\text{brokerage}_{i,t}, \text{brokerage}_{i,t}^2, \text{techdist}_{i,t}, \text{techdist}_{i,t}^2, \text{pre}_{i,t}, \text{degree}_{i,t}, \text{topology}_t) \quad (1)$$

for firm i , with cumulative leading output in the time span $t + \delta_0 \leq \gamma \leq t + \delta_1$.

Through this temporal setup, we explicitly take the intended direction of causality into account. We untangle the assumed reciprocal relationship between standardization and innovation output, as the effect of more innovation firms being more active standardization is excluded from the model.

As our dependent variable is a count variable taking on positive integer values (patent counts), we consider Poisson and Negative Binomial (NB) regression as model candidates (Hausman et al., 1984). Some

authors argue against using Poisson in the presence of overdispersion (which is the case for our data), and accordingly, NB is often used to regress on panel counts. However, using fixed effects in a negative binomial specification is problematic and fixed effects Poisson is generally considered more robust (Guimarães, 2008). Further, there are estimators (e.g., in Stata) that provide robust standard errors in case of misspecified dispersion (Wooldridge, 1999). As available estimators are also robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation in the dependent (patent) variable, we model the relationship with Poisson panel regression with year and firm fixed effects and robust standard errors (estimations performed in Stata 15).

3.4. Variables

Innovation (DV). We use firms' patenting behavior as an indicator of their innovation output. We specifically chose to measure patent applications instead of granted patents, in order to avoid having to deal with grant lags while acknowledging that this eliminates the “quality filter” established by grants. We count transnational patents (Frietsch & Schmoch, 2010) to prevent double counting similar applications made at multiple patent offices. Transnational patents are defined as patents that are traced back to Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) applications plus direct applications at the European Patent Office (EPO) without precursory PCT applications. As most firms in our analysis are French, or at least European, we expect this method of counting to sufficiently capture patent output.

We further restricted counts to “relevant” patent applications, which are those that are technologically related to the input from the analyzed field of standardization. More advanced techniques, such as mapping standards via SEPs (Baron & Pohlmann, 2018), were not feasible due to the low number of SEPs related to our sample. Existing ICS–International Patent Classification (IPC) concordance definitions (e.g., Blind & Thumm, 2004) were too narrow, as manually tracing back patent outputs to firms' standardization activities showed.⁴

We, therefore, generated a new concordance list based on a manual standard- and patent-analysis in which we matched descriptors (keywords) of ICS 71.100 standards with those of patent IPC classes (similar to Ranganathan & Rosenkopf, 2014). The results are shown in Table A.3. In the following sections, we refer to this filtered number as *chemical patent applications*. In order to make our results robust to subjective selection bias, we also test our model on the total, unfiltered number of *all patent applications* and the number of *granted patents*, either filtered or unfiltered.

Technological distance (IV). The technological distance between two firms can be measured by their patenting behavior. Measures are based, e.g., on the dissimilarity of patent citations (Ranganathan et al., 2018), or the distribution of patent classes in firms' patent portfolios (Bar & Leiponen, 2012, 2014; Nambisan, 2013; Yan & Luo, 2016). Common distance functions applied to patent class vectors are Euclidian distance, cosine distance, covariance, or Herfindahl index (e.g., Bar & Leiponen, 2012; Benner & Waldfogel, 2008; Phelps, 2010). Noting the necessity to exclude “irrelevant patent classes” (classes that one of two firms is not active in) from the calculation of distance, Bar and Leiponen (2012) further propose the “Min-Complement Distance Measure”.

We select a metric of technological distance based on the following requirements:

- (a) The metric should reflect the dissimilarity of two firms' technological knowledge at the time of interaction in standardization, and should

⁴ E.g., NF EN 14624:2005 (on refrigerants) associated with a standardizing firm's 2009 patent (EP2221559A1) on lubricant circulation (in refrigerators), filed under mechanical engineering.

³ <https://www.iso.org/developing-standards.html>

- (b) be available for as many firms in the sample as possible. As we argue that firms can use standardization to source distant knowledge, the metric should also
- (c) consider the knowledge that is only available to one of two interacting firms.

In order to fulfill the temporal requirement and to be able to construct the metric for non-patenting firms, we use the *standard authorship history* to represent firms' positions in the knowledge space.

In analogy to patent portfolio vectors, and similar to a method used by [Gauch and Blind \(2015\)](#), we construct "standard portfolio" vectors that represent a firm's position in all firms' knowledge space. Each component (one for each ICS class) of such standard-portfolio vectors $\kappa_{i,t}$ is equal to the number of standards that are categorized in the respective ICS class, that were published before T and that were (co-) authored by firm f_i .

There are 40 (top-level) ICS classes (01,03,07,11,13,...,97); each standard d is associated with ≥ 1 classes ICS_d . The portfolios are, therefore, defined as $\kappa_{i,t} = (|D_{i,t,c}|)$ for classes $c = 01,03,07, \dots$ and $D_{i,t,c} = \{d \mid d \in D_\gamma \wedge \gamma < T \wedge f_i \in F_d \wedge c \in ICS_d\}$.

We assume that the knowledge distance can be described by the cosine distance between these vectors and that the heterogeneity in a group of firms is proportional to the average of the distances. We, therefore, define the technological distance of firm f_i in year t as the average cosine distance between its own and its direct neighbors' $f_j \in N_i(i)$ portfolios:

$$\text{techdist}_{i,t} = \frac{1}{|N_i(i)|} \sum_{f_j \in N_i(i)} 1 - \frac{\kappa_{i,t} \cdot \kappa_{j,t}}{\|\kappa_{i,t}\| \|\kappa_{j,t}\|} \quad (2)$$

Brokerage (IV). We evaluate firms' position by their betweenness centrality ([Freeman, 1977](#)). Betweenness centrality describes how many of the shortest paths in a network run through a node. It is defined as

$$\text{brokerage}_{i,t} = \sum_{f_a, f_b \in F_i} \frac{p_t(a, b \mid i)}{p_t(a, b)} \quad (3)$$

where $p_t(a, b)$ is the number of shortest paths between firms a and b , and $p_t(a, b \mid i)$ the number of such paths that pass through firm i . We normalize betweenness centrality by dividing by the squared number of nodes in the network in order to make values comparable over time.

Controls. We model the relationship between firms' activity in the standardization network and their innovation output using panel regression and, in order to account for unobserved heterogeneity, introduce firm-level fixed effects (as, e.g. [Ahuja, 2000](#); [Bar & Leiponen, 2014](#); [Leiponen, 2008](#); [Ranganathan & Rosenkopf, 2014](#); [Schilling & Phelps, 2007](#)).

We argue that this helps dealing with firm-level omitted variable bias that is not time-relevant in our window of analysis. This is especially relevant for known antecedents of (the extent of) participation in standardization, such as firm size, market position, etc., and unknown firm-level factors that could affect knowledge exchange, as, e.g., experts' propensity of disclosing information in informal settings.

However, fixed effects do not account for confounders that affect innovation output and vary with time, either on the firm level (e.g., R&D expenses) or for the whole industry/network, in- or decreasing the overall level of innovation (e.g., caused by external shocks, such as the 2008 financial crisis). We argue that controlling for firm-level pre-sample innovation and varying network topology accounts for both kinds of endogeneity.

We include firms' degrees, i.e., the number of co-developing firms, as a model variable. The more standards a firm develops, the more co-developers it is connected to. We, therefore, argue that degree is a proxy for the extent of participation. Arguably, more participation is associated with higher innovation outcome ([Zhang et al., 2020](#)). Therefore, only by controlling for the extent of participation, we can consider firms' network positions and technological dissimilarities as causes of innovation outcomes.

The most evident source of time-dependent heterogeneity in firms' innovation output after collaboration in standardization stems from their "inherent innovativeness", that is, their varying prior propensity to produce innovations. This can be assumed to be proportional to properties related to the input to the innovation process, such as R&D expenses, but also, as we are measuring *patents* as an indicators of innovation, contingent upon patenting behavior and appropriability conditions ([Ahuja et al., 2008](#)).

Similar to [Schilling and Phelps \(2007\)](#), we, therefore, control for the aggregate number of patents a firm has been granted in a window before its activity in standardization ("pre-sample patents", [Blundell et al., 1995](#)). We argue that this, following the same argumentation as for our dependent variable, is an indicator of innovation while it also incorporates the same patenting-specific firm properties. We follow [Phelps \(2010\)](#) in setting the window to five years.

We control for the networks' time-dependent overall structure as determining factor for knowledge flows and resulting innovation output levels. Following [Schilling and Phelps \(2007\)](#), we represent network topology by the features density, reach and clustering. *Density* measures the ratio of the existing number to the potential number of links. A denser network contributes to faster diffusion of information. *Reach* describes how well firms' knowledge reaches other firms on average. The shorter the average shortest path between firms, the higher the reach. This corresponds to the metric of distance-weighted reach used by [Schilling and Phelps \(2007\)](#), who argue that shorter paths, i.e. less firms involved in a transmission channel, enable information to spread more quickly and with less distortion. A firm's *clustering* coefficient is the fraction of triangles formed with its neighbors. The more links exist between a firm's neighbors, the higher the coefficient. Clustering, the average of all firms' coefficients, describes the extent to which potential links between related firms are formed.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows summary statistics of the generated panel data set and the documents and authors used for generation. The data set is based on authorship information of 416 standards with ICS class 71.100 (*products of the chemical industry*) that were published by AFNOR between 2000 and 2010. As we considered a development phase of 3 years, the panel ends in 2007. After cleaning names, a total of 406 organizations (excluding standards-setting organizations (SSOs) AFNOR and European Committee for Standardization (CEN)) could be identified as authors, including 259 firms, 69 associations or federations, 21 research institutes, 16 ministries, and 21 consumer representatives (21 remained unknown).

The panel is unbalanced as organizations enter into and leave standard development during the time span. Please note that we used *all* ICS classes for the calculation of technological distance, which is not depicted in the table. Also note that we calculate the two explanatory variables brokerage (betweenness centrality) and technological distance using all organizations in the network, however, only patenting organizations (firms) are included in the panel regression, as we cannot measure the innovation output of the non-patenting organizations.

Following the model in Section 3.2, we generated one co-authorship network for each year. Firms collaborated with an average of about 34 to 38 co-authors. In each year, 213 to 273 organizations were involved, including 127 to 165 firms.

There was a rather small overlap in authorship between standards, meaning that most organizations appeared to be active in only a few groups at the same time. The underlying authorship groups, therefore, produced networks that were sparse but clustered (density = 0.12 to 0.18, avg. clustering = 0.90 to 0.94).

Fig. 3 shows a visualization of an aggregation of the networks from 2000 to 2007 with an indication of brokerage status (betweenness

Table 1
Descriptive statistics.

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
Standards under development ^a	47	89	139	210	201	167	107	94
Active organizations	233	239	252	273	269	232	213	230
Active firms	138	136	146	165	164	139	127	141
Mean number of authors	33.6 (14.5)	24.4 (13.7)	20.8 (16.4)	25.6 (22.0)	30.5 (23.6)	34.3 (22.5)	38.8 (20.4)	37.1 (21.7)
Networks								
Density	0.158	0.144	0.136	0.124	0.128	0.153	0.177	0.158
Reach	0.290	0.271	0.226	0.217	0.232	0.239	0.192	0.194
Clustering	0.899	0.916	0.921	0.920	0.929	0.945	0.933	0.928
Mean degree	36.4 (21.0)	33.8 (19.9)	33.7 (20.1)	33.4 (19.5)	34.0 (18.9)	35.1 (18.3)	37.7 (16.3)	36.3 (15.9)
Mean degree, firms	33.6 (19.3)	32.1 (18.0)	31.8 (18.3)	31.3 (16.9)	31.3 (16.6)	33.0 (16.4)	35.4 (14.3)	33.8 (13.8)
Betweenness centrality (%)								
Mean	0.356 (1.80)	0.379 (2.07)	0.422 (2.36)	0.409 (2.15)	0.434 (2.40)	0.460 (2.75)	0.538 (2.61)	0.511 (2.23)
Max	20.5	24.0	24.1	22.6	23.1	30.2	21.8	17.4
Technological distance								
Mean	0.909 (0.064)	0.918 (0.061)	0.920 (0.058)	0.924 (0.054)	0.922 (0.053)	0.904 (0.059)	0.883 (0.058)	0.897 (0.052)
Patent applications^b								
Mean, all	238.6 (819.0)	150.6 (618.5)	169.3 (658.2)	163.2 (675.8)	155.4 (703.2)	138.8 (734.5)	133.7 (764.7)	128.5 (733.3)
Mean, chemical	178.3 (727.4)	99.2 (530.2)	96.6 (551.3)	94.8 (567.0)	94.3 (597.0)	92.6 (630.3)	104.0 (681.2)	100.4 (669.6)
chemical, % of all	74.8	65.9	57.0	58.1	60.7	66.7	77.7	78.1

^a ICS 71.100 (products of the chemical industry).

^b Aggregated, 2–5 year lead.

centrality). The distribution of brokerage (betweenness centrality, BC) was right-skewed. Most organizations (94%) did not have any broker status, as none (0%) or very few (< 1%) of the networks' shortest paths ran through them ($BC = 0$: 40%, $BC < 1\%$: 54%). Many organizations with very high broker status were non-patenting government entities or industry associations.

Of all 259 participating firms, 143 (55%) had filed at least one patent application under PCT and/or at the EPO in the time span of 2001 to 2012. Per year, firms applied for an average of 41 (all patents) and 28 (chemical patents). The distributions of patent application counts were all heavily right-skewed and long-tailed with 4-year cumulative maxima of > 1000 applications per firm.

In total, chemical patent applications made up 57% (in 2004) to 78% (in 2007) of all applications. The main spillover areas (IPC classes other than *chemical*) were electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, measuring, transportation, and civil engineering. This corresponds to firms' activity in other standardization areas (Fig. 4). However, not all standardization complements were reflected in patents (e.g., construction, food).

Aggregated over the period of two to five years after standard-setting activity, patenting firms in brokerage positions ($BC > 0$) had, on average, applied for more patents than those not in brokerage positions (chemical patent applications: $M_{BC>0} = 148.2$, $M_{BC=0} = 43.9$). A negative binomial regression of these patent application counts (all/chemical) on normalized BC confirmed a significant association ($p < 0.05$).

Based on the data of prior authorship, we generated ICS distribution vectors for each year and organization in our sample. We then calculated pairwise technological distances as discussed in Section 3.4. The portfolios showed that the development of chemical standards involved diverse backgrounds with histories of standardization activity in other technological areas.

The 406 participating organizations generated a combined history of 145,154 (co-) authorships prior to 2007. On average, they co-authored documents in 7.4 top-level classes ($SD = 7.3$, $max = 39$). Most authored documents were filed under *Environment, health protection, safety* (16.5%), *Construction materials and building* (13.8%), and

Fig. 3. Network of organizations involved in standardizing products of the chemical industry at AFNOR. Node size: betweenness centrality, color: community (Leiden alg.).2000–2007, $k=3$.

Chemical technology (9.2%). Representing the focal area of activity by the most commonly co-authored ICS class showed that less than half (40.6%) of the organizations had their main focus on chemical technology (Fig. 4, bottom left). Other relevant focal areas were fluid systems, construction, environment, health and safety, wood technology, etc.

The co-occurrence of ICS classes in the organizations' co-authorship portfolios followed specific patterns. High correlations suggested the mirroring of underlying complements in technological applications such as construction and glass & ceramics; health care, paper technology, and rubber & plastics; or manufacturing, fluid systems, and electrical engineering. The investigation of technological distances showed that firms were positioned in meaningful technology clusters that corresponded to their focal technological areas.

Fig. 4 shows a 2-dimensional projection of firms' ICS portfolios. We used Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) (McInnes et al., 2018) instead of, e.g., Principal Component Analysis

Fig. 4. Technological distance. Projection of organizations' positions in knowledge space (UMAP of technological distance). Colors: Focal technological areas (most common co-authored ICS class).

(PCA) to allow for non-linear relationships. We identified four knowledge clusters that were robust to different UMAP parameter settings. The clusters showed the following distinct technological focuses: chemical technology (cluster 1), paint and color (2), wood technology and construction (4), and natural and applied sciences mixed with chemical technology (5).

We performed linear regression of organization type (*firm, association, end-user organization, public authority or research institute*) and the interaction with betweenness centrality on technological distance while controlling for year ($F(16, 1754) = 28.3, p < 0.001, \text{adj. } R^2 = 0.2$). This showed that, on average, firms collaborated with slightly but significantly more diverse partners than end-user organizations, associations and research institutes, but less significantly more diverse partners than public entities. The exception were associations and end-user organizations in brokerage positions (coefficient of type \times betweenness centrality > 1). Interestingly, the overall association between brokerage and technological distance was significantly negative, meaning that the more organizations bridged structural holes, the more homogeneous their direct neighbors.

4.2. Regression analysis

Table 2 reports estimates from Poisson panel regression with robust standard errors for the relationship between technological distance, brokerage and delayed patent output. All variables except pre-sample patents are standardized, so that the coefficients can be interpreted as the effect on patent applications by one standard deviation change of the independent variable. The dependent variables of all models are the cumulative count of firms' patent applications two to five years after collaboration in the network.

The results show that betweenness centrality (brokerage) and technological distance are significantly associated with delayed (leading) patent output. They also confirm the significant influence of pre-sample patents, which control for existing knowledge stocks and patenting behaviors. These results are consistent when regressing on the portion of patent output that is directly related to the standardization efforts (chemical patents), and when regressing on all patents. This could indicate that knowledge exchange in standardization has beneficial effects that spill beyond technological boundaries in firms. Interestingly, the number of co-authors (degree), is not significantly associated with delayed (leading) patent output. This shows that firms' extent of participation does not sufficiently explain innovation outcomes. Estimates for the variables that control for yearly global network topology draw are also consistent.

4.3. Non-linear effects

We hypothesized that both the relationships between technological distance and innovation output (Hypothesis 1) and betweenness centrality and innovation output (Hypothesis 2) are non-linear, specifically having inverted U-shapes. We followed the recommendations given by Lind and Mehlum (2010) and Haans et al. (2015) to evaluate the presence of (inverted) U-shapes.

The first criterion, significant quadratic terms, is met in case of both hypotheses (coefficients of BC \times BC, TD \times TD significant and negative for all models, see Table 2). We conducted the test proposed by Lind and Mehlum (2010), using the Fieller method to construct the confidence interval of the turning point. The tests results support an inverted U-shaped for both technological distance and brokerage (see Table A.5).

Following Haans et al. (2015), we further plotted the predicted margins of technological distance and brokerage, to visually investigate turning points and slopes (Fig. 5). To be able to assess the relevance of the effect-shape in relation to the distribution of our data, we report the range of the x-axis as multiples of the standard deviation.

Both charts show inverted U-shapes, confirming the performed tests. The left-hand chart shows the predicted margin of technological distance in two standard deviations around the mean. The positive effect peaks at low to medium values of technological distance and continuously decreases with higher values. The x-axis of the right-hand chart is extended to include the extreme point. It shows that for the most relevant range of brokerage positions realized in the sample, the effect of more brokerage potential is almost linearly positive. The relationship peaks outside more than four standard deviations from the mean and lies within a very large confidence interval. Apparently, the effect of brokerage is inverted U-shaped, however, the latent negative effect (integration costs) appears to only become relevant at very high levels of brokerage in the sample.

We predicted that firms' innovation output is associated with brokerage status and that the relationship is inverse U-shaped (Hypothesis 2). Both linear and quadratic relationships are significant, and the coefficient for the quadratic term is negative, which implies that the hypothesis can be confirmed. However, the contribution of the quadratic relationship is very small. Fig. 5 (right) shows that for the most relevant range of brokerage positions realized in the sample, the effect of more brokerage potential is almost linearly positive. The relationship peaks outside more than four standard deviations from the mean and lies within a very large confidence interval.

We, therefore, argue that our results only conclusively confirm a positive association. According to Hypothesis 1, we further predicted that a firm's innovation output has an inverted U-shaped relationship

Table 2
Estimation results from Poisson panel regression with robust standard errors.

	Chemical patent applications		All patent applications	
	FE	RE	FE	RE
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Betweenness centrality (BC)	0.383*** (0.0621)	0.389*** (0.0593)	0.332*** (0.0608)	0.338*** (0.0551)
BC × BC	-0.0368*** (0.00810)	-0.0421*** (0.00738)	-0.0314** (0.00974)	-0.0383*** (0.00888)
Technological distance (TD)	-0.138 (0.111)	-0.0999 (0.102)	-0.291** (0.112)	-0.202 (0.122)
TD × TD	-0.128** (0.0393)	-0.110** (0.0384)	-0.127*** (0.0330)	-0.102** (0.0342)
Degree	0.0303 (0.0532)	0.0302 (0.0517)	-0.0901 (0.0782)	-0.0554 (0.0806)
pre-sample patents (chemical)	0.906*** (0.0908)	0.935*** (0.0625)		
pre-sample patents (all)			0.932*** (0.0775)	0.953*** (0.0519)
Density	-0.0362* (0.0143)	-0.0367** (0.0136)	-0.00746 (0.0159)	-0.00871 (0.0164)
Reach	-0.0442** (0.0139)	-0.0402** (0.0146)	-0.0273* (0.0123)	-0.0229 (0.0138)
Clustering	-0.0454* (0.0194)	-0.0489** (0.0185)	-0.0747*** (0.0216)	-0.0770*** (0.0216)
Reach × Clustering	0.0110 (0.0151)	0.0103 (0.0149)	0.0326* (0.0158)	0.0325 (0.0166)
Constant		0.935** (0.287)		0.846*** (0.241)
Observations	314	323	448	457
AIC	1492.9	2307.0	2423.3	3554.1

Year and firm-level fixed effects (FE), random effects (RE).

Robust standard errors in parentheses.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. 5. Predicted margins of technological distance and brokerage with 95% CI (regression model 2 random effects).

with the technological distance to its standards co-authors. The estimated coefficient of technological distance *squared* is significant and negative. The linear relationship is not significant. Fig. 5 (left) shows the marginal effect of technological distance in two standard deviations around the mean. The positive effect peaks at low to medium values of technological distance and continuously decreases with higher values. We conclude that our regression results confirm Hypothesis 1.

4.4. Robustness

We tested different model specifications and parameters to ensure robustness. First, we tested whether Poisson panel regression with random effects could be a more efficient model. As Table 2 shows, estimation with random effects produced very similar coefficients and standard errors, which would have led to the same conclusions. Based on a Hausman test with $p < 0.001$, we stuck to the conditional fixed

effects instead of evaluating our hypotheses based on the random effects estimation.

Next, we tested negative binomial panel regression models with fixed year and firm effects. This model also produced very consistent estimates for both configurations of dependent variables.

We further investigated different patenting delays. The dependent variables in our main models were based on the cumulative sum of patent applications in a five year window after standardization activity, minus the counts in the first year. We subtracted the first year, as we gathered that delays as short as a few weeks could simply not constitute time spans that would allow firms to absorb, process, and translate knowledge into patent applications. To relax this assumption, we also modeled delays from 1–5 years and 3–5 years.

Table A.4 shows results for Poisson panel regression with robust standard errors and fixed year and firm-level effects. Overall, the estimations were consistent with our main model. We argue that the results

confirm both our hypotheses, with the caveat, that the inverted U-shape of the relationship between brokerage and innovation output was only relevant for the extrem right-end part of the sample distribution.

5. Discussion

The aim of our analysis was to investigate the relationship between participation in standardization and firm-level innovation. While prior research suggested that more participation leads to higher innovation output (e.g., Zhang et al., 2020) there was a lack of empirical findings concerning underlying causality.

Our findings show that firms that take on brokerage positions in-between standard-setting groups subsequently exhibit increased levels of patent applications. We interpret this as an effect of increased innovation that results from access to more knowledge sources and more knowledge diversity.

This potentially confirms assumptions by Zhang et al. (2020), who interpret higher innovation output after standardization activity as a result of the improvement of firms' R&D efficiency through access to specific knowledge about the development of technological trajectories, and the increased number of firms' innovation partners and extended knowledge transfer through collaborative innovation.

We further find that technological distance in standard-setting groups overall had a negative U-shaped relationship with delayed patent applications. We see this as a confirmation of Hypothesis 1 and an extension of findings by Nambisan (2013). These findings are also consistent with more general findings for interfirm learning in strategic alliances (Subramanian et al., 2018).

Our results suggest that the latent effects that diminish returns from brokerage only set in at very high levels. This does not necessarily invalidate the assumptions that led to Hypothesis 2. One explanation lies in the properties of the sampled network, which exhibits a highly clustered structure. This mirrors most organizations' focus on the development of a single standard, which implied that simultaneous participation in the development of a few standards could already put other organizations into prominent brokerage positions. Interpreting the very right-skewed distribution of betweenness centrality in standard deviations from the mean, therefore, overemphasizes the meaning of "high levels" of brokerage.

Another explanation for diminishing returns at very high levels of brokerage is the trade-off between knowledge diversity and bandwidth (Aral & Van Alstyne, 2011). By connecting technologically diverse fields, brokers potentially create more weak and indirect ties. However, as standardization often involves very complex knowledge, brokers need to complement weak and indirect ties (more diverse knowledge) with strong direct ties (more complex knowledge) in order to pursue both exploitative and exploratory innovation (Tiwana, 2008). This corresponds with our finding that higher levels of brokerage were associated with higher technological proximity to direct partners. It suggests that diminishing returns from the potentially rising difficulty of integrating knowledge from a growing number of sources is mitigated by less diversity in local interactions.

Our results particularly relate to findings from a new product development context by Wen et al. (2020), who investigate the relationship between Chinese automotive firms' standardization network positions and their product speed to market (STM) and new product introduction rate (NPIR). Wen et al. (2020) find that firms that bridge more structural holes (similar to our brokerage variable) introduce fewer new vehicle models (slower NPIR) but announce this earlier in the year (faster STM). Our results are in line with this knowledge-exchange-perspective and are evidence of the relevance of the mechanism for earlier stages in the new product development process.

That we, contrary to Wen et al. (2020), find a positive relationship between brokerage (bridging structural holes) and firm output that is explained by knowledge-exchange (new patents/new product introductions) could be due to our approach of modeling knowledge

heterogeneity. Wen et al. (2020), on the one hand, argue that firms that interact with brokers that span structural holes are more likely to hesitate to reveal knowledge which could be more likely to be passed to competitors. We, on the other hand, argue that spanning structural holes and the associated growth in knowledge heterogeneity and complexity particularly raises challenges for knowledge integration by brokers. The difference between the negative (Wen et al.) and the positive relationship (this paper) between brokerage and firm innovation (in analogy to new production introduction) might be explained by the explicit inclusion of knowledge heterogeneity through technological distance, which would support our line of argument.

5.1. Limitations

There are some limitations to this study that should be addressed by future research.

First, there are limitations related to sample selection and the necessary model assumptions. The focus on a single industry limits the generalizability of this study. Furthermore, the associated truncation of both independent (sub-network) and dependent variables (chemical patents) mean that there are potential knowledge flows and innovation outcomes which we cannot account for.

While we test the robustness of including only selected patent areas in our model, we cannot do the same for the selected sub-network, as modeling the complete network turned out to be infeasible with our methodological approach and resources. Firms' diverse participation in standardizing in different ICS fields indeed shows that a part of the information on firms' embeddedness in the whole standardization network is missing.

The focus on a very knowledge-intensive area might further lead to different results than the analysis of areas where the balance between knowledge-seeking and rule-shaping motives is shifted. In more integrated, more complex, and more rapidly changing industries than the chemical products industry, more information asymmetries and less regulatory capture could be associated with stronger effects on firm-level innovation (Blind et al., 2017b).

In future research, more extensive studies could integrate the networks of different standard-setting contexts, e.g., across industries, and different standardization settings, such as industry consortia, and SSOs on different regional levels.

Second, there are limitations that are related to our approach of dealing with endogeneity by employing fixed (or random) effects to capture time-invariant firm-specific heterogeneity. In case that more innovative firms participate differently, or firms join committees in anticipation of upcoming innovations, resulting reverse causality would violate the assumption of strict endogeneity.

We explicitly deal with reverse causality by lagging the independent variables and controlling for a lagged version of the dependent variable (pre-sample patents). It could be argued that this approach might not be sufficient as there is uncertainty about the precise temporal relationships and the timing of causal effects. Furthermore, time-variant heterogeneity could still be an issue, for example, introduced by firms' changing R&D expenditures. Another draw-back of the fixed effects approach is that it "only" identifies the average treatment effect on the treated, which in this case means firms that have changed brokerage positions, disregarding those that remain in the same position.

However, as brokerage positions are not only determined by the individual firms' decisions, but the overall formation of the network, we are less concerned with this issue. For a more definitive assessment of the causal effect, further research using (quasi-) experimental setups would certainly be desirable.

Finally, it has to be noted that our dependent variable *patent applications* does not incorporate patent quality, as could *granted patents* or new product introductions. Our primary reason to not simply use granted patent indicator was the unclear grant lag. Counting applications of

granted patents and referring to their filing date could have theoretically alleviated that problem. However, the alignment between patent applications and granted patent is not necessarily that clear. Between filing and grant decision, applicants can generate further output, such as amendments or divisionals (e.g., Berger et al., 2012). Due to our perspective that focuses on knowledge flows, this (the introduction of later input) dissolves the association with standard-setting behavior in our panel. Applicants' pre-grant behavior would also need to be considered, e.g., in case of withdrawn applications and patent blocking strategies. Furthermore, grant decisions can be affected by administrative changes, which could introduce time-dependency into our fixed effects model.

The selection of another patent quality metric, or other metrics such as new product introductions, would have potentially introduced similar problems (e.g., Higham et al., 2021) and would have considerably shifted our methodological focus. Rather than focusing on optimal patent metrics, future research could try to investigate how knowledge-exchange in standardization networks impacts later stages of new product development.

6. Conclusion

The results of this study underline that firms can foster innovation by participating in standardization. This confirms the knowledge-seeking strategies already pursued by some standardizing firms (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016), but also adds new aspects that need to be considered to optimize innovation potentials.

The positive effects from attaining brokerage positions and the relevance of technological heterogeneity show that it can pay off for firms to strategically join more distant fora. However, for sourcing new knowledge from standardization, firms not only need to consider the technological relatedness of committees they consider joining (Nambisan, 2013), but also need to take into account the roles of other

participants in the overall knowledge network. By incorporating information about the structure and content of underlying knowledge networks into their standardization strategies, firms can optimize access to relevant new knowledge.

The significance of knowledge exchange in standardization as an innovation-fostering mechanism corroborates the idea that standard-setting should be treated as open innovation activity and needs to be better linked to new product development processes (Großmann et al., 2015).

Standard-setting organizations and other participating stakeholders need to improve conditions that promote knowledge exchange. By simplifying access for diverse actors such as start-ups or open source organizations, they can contribute to creating a more diversified knowledge landscape that increases the potential for product innovation that is driven by participation in standardization.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Philipp Heß: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Magnus Buggenhagen:** Data curation, Conceptualization. **Knut Blind:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Appendix. Additional tables

Table A.3
Patent areas related to ICS 71.100.

	Area and field	IPC
I	Electrical engineering	
1	Electrical machinery, apparatus, energy	F21#, H01B, H01C, H01F, H01G, H01H, H01J, H01K, H01M, H01R, H01T, H02#, H05B, H05C, H05F, H99Z
II	Instruments	
9	Optics	G02#, G03B, G03C, G03D, G03F, G03G, G03H, H01S, G02#, G03B, G03C, G03D, G03F, G03G, G03H, H01S
10	Measurements	G01B, G01C, G01D, G01F, G01G, G01H, G01J, G01K, G01L, G01M, (G01N not G01N-033), G01P, G01R, G01S; G01V, G01W, G04#, G12B, G99Z
11	Analysis of biological materials	G01N-033
12	Control	G05B, G05D, G05F, G07#, G08B, G08G, G09B, G09C, G09D
13	Medical technology	A61B, A61C, A61D, A61F, A61G, A61H, A61J, A61L, A61M, A61N, H05G
III	Chemistry	
14	Organic fine chemistry	(C07B, C07C, C07D, C07F, C07H, C07J, C40B) not A61K, A61K-008, A61Q
15	Biotechnology	(C07G, C07K, C12M, C12N, C12P, C12Q, C12R, C12S) not A61K
16	Pharmaceuticals	A61K not A61K-008
17	Macromolecular chemistry, polymers	C08B, C08C, C08F, C08G, C08H, C08K, C08L
18	Food chemistry	A01H, A21D, A23B, A23C, A23D, A23F, A23G, A23J, A23K, A23L, C12C, C12F, C12G, C12H, C12J, C13D, C13F, C13J, C13K

(continued on next page)

Table A.3 (continued).

	Area and field	IPC
19	Basic, materials chemistry	A01N, A01P, C05#, C06#, C09B, C09C, C09F, C09G, C09H, C09K, C09D, C09J, C10B, C10C, C10F, C10G, C10H, C10J, C10K, C10L, C10M, C10N, C11B, C11C, C11D, C99Z
20	Materials, metallurgy	C01#, C03C, C04#, C21#, C22#, B22#
21	Surface, technology, coating	B05C, B05D, B32#, C23#, C25#, C30#
22	Micro-structure, and nano-technology	B81#, B82#
23	Chemical engineering	B01B, B01D-000#, B01D-01##, B01D-02##, B01D-03##, B01D-041, B01D-043, B01D-057, B01D-059, B01D-06##, B01D-07##, B01F, B01J, B01L, B02C, B03#, B04#, B05B, B06B, B07##, B08#, D06B, D06C, D06L, F25J, F26#, C14C, H05H
24	Environmental technology	A62D, B01D-045, B01D-046, B01D-047, B01D-049, B01D-050, B01D-051, B01D-052, B01D-053, B09#, B65F, C02#, F01N, F23G, F23J, G01T, E01F-008, A62C
IV	Mechanical engineering	
25	Handling	B25J, B65B, B65C, B65D, B65G, B65H, B66#, B67#
26	Machine tools	B21#, B23#, B24#, B26D, B26F, B27#, B30#, B25B, B25C, B25D, B25F, B25G, B25H, B26B
27	Engines, pumps, turbines	F01B, F01C, F01D, F01K, F01L, F01M, F01P, F02#, F03#, F04#, F23R, G21#, F99Z
28	Textile and paper machines	A41H, A43D, A46D, C14B, D01#, D02#, D03#, D04B, D04C, D04G, D04H, D05#, D06G, D06H, D06J, D06M, D06P, D06Q, D99Z, B31#, D21#, B41#
29	Other special machines	A01B, A01C, A01D, A01F, A01G, A01J, A01K, A01L, A01M, A21B, A21C, A22#, A23N, A23P, B02B, C12L, C13C, C13G, C13H, B28#, B29#, C03B, C08J, B99Z, F41#, F42#
30	Thermal processes and apparatus	F22#, F23B, F23C, F23D, F23H, F23K, F23L, F23M, F23N, F23Q, F24#, F25B, F25C, F27#, F28#
31	Mechanical elements	F15#, F16#, F17#, G05G
32	Transport	B60#, B61#, B62#, B63B, B63C, B63G, B63H, B63J, B64#
V	Other fields	
35	Civil engineering	E02#, E01B, E01C, E01D, E01F-001, E01F-003, E01F-005, E01F-007, E01F-009, E01F-01#, E01H, E03#, E04#, E05#, E06#, E21#, E99Z

Table A.4

Additional regression estimations (robustness check).

Dependent var.	Patent applications (chemical)							Patent applications (all)						
	P	NB	P	P	P	P	P	NB	P	P	P	P	P	
Accum. delay (years)	2-5	2-5	1-5	2-5	3-5	4-5	5	2-5	2-5	1-5	2-5	3-5	4-5	5
BC	0.383*** (0.0621)	0.322*** (0.0742)	0.208*** (0.0419)	0.383*** (0.0621)	0.546*** (0.0847)	0.555*** (0.143)	0.680*** (0.182)	0.332*** (0.0608)	0.273*** (0.0375)	0.173*** (0.0608)	0.332*** (0.0608)	0.468*** (0.104)	0.488** (0.158)	0.486* (0.195)
BC × BC	-0.0368*** (0.00810)	-0.0396** (0.0129)	-0.0205*** (0.00494)	-0.0368*** (0.00810)	-0.0349* (0.0160)	-0.0334 (0.0333)	-0.0796** (0.0265)	-0.0314** (0.00974)	-0.0234* (0.0116)	-0.0227*** (0.00458)	-0.0314** (0.00974)	-0.0269 (0.0185)	-0.0243 (0.0332)	-0.0555 (0.0334)
TD	-0.138 (0.111)	-0.0302 (0.124)	-0.109 (0.0916)	-0.138 (0.111)	-0.135 (0.143)	0.0963 (0.226)	0.397 (0.495)	-0.291** (0.112)	-0.292** (0.106)	-0.127 (0.116)	-0.291** (0.112)	-0.429** (0.144)	-0.455* (0.191)	-0.202 (0.301)
TD × TD	-0.128** (0.0393)	-0.0664* (0.0318)	-0.0665* (0.0297)	-0.128** (0.0393)	-0.205*** (0.0533)	-0.190* (0.0747)	-0.136 (0.126)	-0.127*** (0.0330)	-0.114*** (0.0251)	-0.0453 (0.0248)	-0.127*** (0.0330)	-0.211*** (0.0520)	-0.230** (0.0710)	-0.152 (0.102)
Degree	0.0303 (0.0532)	0.0539 (0.0985)	0.000452 (0.0811)	0.0303 (0.0532)	0.0795 (0.0711)	0.288* (0.125)	0.469 (0.290)	-0.0901 (0.0782)	-0.0884 (0.0883)	-0.0364 (0.0961)	-0.0901 (0.0782)	-0.140 (0.106)	-0.115 (0.161)	0.0381 (0.198)
Pre. pat. (chem.)	0.906*** (0.0908)	1.031*** (0.0368)	0.851*** (0.0920)	0.906*** (0.0908)	0.969*** (0.110)	0.952*** (0.147)	0.944*** (0.190)							
Pre. pat. (all)								0.932*** (0.0775)	0.965*** (0.0261)	0.892*** (0.0728)	0.932*** (0.0775)	0.934*** (0.0955)	0.854*** (0.117)	0.736*** (0.137)
Density	-0.0362* (0.0143)	-0.0322 (0.0184)	-0.00134 (0.0131)	-0.0362* (0.0143)	-0.105*** (0.0202)	-0.175*** (0.0371)	-0.194*** (0.0457)	-0.00746 (0.0159)	-0.00739 (0.0154)	0.0234 (0.0152)	-0.00746 (0.0159)	-0.0580** (0.0202)	-0.0807* (0.0336)	-0.0716 (0.0427)
Reach	-0.0442*** (0.0139)	-0.0354** (0.0119)	-0.0290** (0.0111)	-0.0442*** (0.0139)	-0.0722*** (0.0196)	-0.0921*** (0.0255)	-0.0714*** (0.0189)	-0.0273* (0.0123)	-0.0298** (0.0114)	-0.00717 (0.0120)	-0.0273* (0.0123)	-0.0464** (0.0174)	-0.0532* (0.0239)	-0.0462 (0.0253)
Clustering	-0.0454* (0.0194)	-0.0442* (0.0222)	-0.0377** (0.0120)	-0.0454* (0.0194)	0.0206 (0.0309)	0.0990 (0.0563)	0.100 (0.0627)	-0.0747*** (0.0216)	-0.0610** (0.0190)	-0.0724*** (0.0170)	-0.0747*** (0.0216)	-0.0196 (0.0278)	0.0216 (0.0423)	0.0114 (0.0464)
Reach × Clustering	0.0110 (0.0151)	0.00667 (0.0216)	0.0121 (0.00955)	0.0110 (0.0151)	-0.0593 (0.0323)	-0.140** (0.0514)	-0.159*** (0.0450)	0.0326* (0.0158)	0.0242 (0.0188)	0.0404** (0.0132)	0.0326* (0.0158)	-0.0215 (0.0228)	-0.0545 (0.0366)	-0.0392 (0.0435)
Observations	314	314	314	314	306	301	288	448	448	448	448	440	426	414
AIC	1492.9	1492.7	1364.4	1492.9	1624.3	1754.0	1541.0	2423.3	2258.5	2199.5	2423.3	2690.2	2826.0	2381.9

P=Poisson panel regression, NB=negative binomial panel regression, both with year and firm-level fixed effects.

Standard errors in parentheses, Poisson with robust SE.

* p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

Table A.5

Test of inverted U-shape following Lind and Mehlum (2010), outputs of “u-test” package in STATA.

	BC	TD
data range	[-0.187; 13.712]	[-4.579; 1.524]
extreme point	4.620	-0.455
slope at lower	0.405***	0.905**
slope at upper	-0.766***	-0.434**
t-value	4.10***	2.13**
95% conf. interval (Fieller method)	[3.225; 6.832]	[-1.086; 1.104]

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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